

Dedicated to Oliver Seely and his friends.

Scherzo

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Allegro

The musical score is presented in three systems, each with four staves. The first system includes parts for Flute, Oboe, B♭ Clarinet, and Bassoon, starting at measure 1. The second system continues from measure 7, and the third system starts at measure 13. The score is written in 3/4 time with a key signature of two flats (B♭ and E♭). The music features a mix of eighth and sixteenth notes, often beamed together, and includes various articulations such as slurs and accents. The bassoon part in the first system has a prominent melodic line with slurs and accents. The woodwind parts in the subsequent systems show more complex rhythmic patterns and melodic development.

2
19 Scherzo

Fl.
Ob.
B♭ Cl.
Bsn.

25

Fl.
Ob.
B♭ Cl.
Bsn.

31

Fl.
Ob.
B♭ Cl.
Bsn.

Scherzo

37

Musical score for measures 37-42. The score is for four instruments: Flute (Fl.), Oboe (Ob.), B♭ Clarinet (B♭ Cl.), and Bassoon (Bsn.). The key signature is two sharps (F# and C#). The Flute part features a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with slurs. The Oboe part has a similar rhythmic pattern. The B♭ Clarinet part has a melodic line with slurs. The Bassoon part has a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with slurs.

43

Musical score for measures 43-48. The score is for four instruments: Flute (Fl.), Oboe (Ob.), B♭ Clarinet (B♭ Cl.), and Bassoon (Bsn.). The key signature is two sharps (F# and C#). The Flute part features a melodic line with slurs and accents. The Oboe part has a similar melodic line. The B♭ Clarinet part has a melodic line with slurs. The Bassoon part has a melodic line with slurs.

49

Musical score for measures 49-54. The score is for four instruments: Flute (Fl.), Oboe (Ob.), B♭ Clarinet (B♭ Cl.), and Bassoon (Bsn.). The key signature is two sharps (F# and C#). The Flute part features a melodic line with slurs and accents, including triplets. The Oboe part has a similar melodic line. The B♭ Clarinet part has a melodic line with slurs. The Bassoon part has a melodic line with slurs.

Scherzo

4 55

Fl.
Ob.
B♭ Cl.
Bsn.

62

Fl.
Ob.
B♭ Cl.
Bsn.

69

Fl.
Ob.
B♭ Cl.
Bsn.

75

Musical score for measures 75-80. The score is for four woodwind instruments: Flute (Fl.), Oboe (Ob.), B♭ Clarinet (B♭ Cl.), and Bassoon (Bsn.). The key signature is B-flat major (two flats). The time signature is 3/4. The Flute part features a melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes, including a triplet in measure 80. The Oboe part has a similar melodic line with some rests. The B♭ Clarinet part plays a rhythmic accompaniment of eighth notes. The Bassoon part plays a similar rhythmic accompaniment in the bass clef.

81

Musical score for measures 81-86. The score is for four woodwind instruments: Flute (Fl.), Oboe (Ob.), B♭ Clarinet (B♭ Cl.), and Bassoon (Bsn.). The key signature is B-flat major (two flats). The time signature is 3/4. The Flute part continues the melodic line with a triplet in measure 82. The Oboe part has a similar melodic line. The B♭ Clarinet part continues the rhythmic accompaniment. The Bassoon part continues the rhythmic accompaniment in the bass clef.

87

Musical score for measures 87-92. The score is for four woodwind instruments: Flute (Fl.), Oboe (Ob.), B♭ Clarinet (B♭ Cl.), and Bassoon (Bsn.). The key signature is B-flat major (two flats). The time signature is 3/4. The Flute part features a melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes, including a triplet in measure 87. The Oboe part has a similar melodic line. The B♭ Clarinet part continues the rhythmic accompaniment. The Bassoon part continues the rhythmic accompaniment in the bass clef.